

The Relationship between Ethical leadership and Teachers Continuance Organizational Commitment

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Abstract:

The current study aims to investigate the relationship between the behavior of ethical leaders EL and their continuance organizational commitment COC, and also to discover the mediational impact of teachers' loyalty TL on their relationships at the international schools in Jeddah, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA).

The study employed a quantitative approach as follows: a formatted questionnaire was distributed to a random sample, of which 372 valid questionnaires were returned to the researchers. In addition to examining the research hypotheses, several statistical methods were used to analyse the compiled data. The study showed that when the supervisor displays positive behaviors and a moral leadership style, this has leverage on the employees' performance. The study found that there is statistically important engagement relevance between ethical leadership EL and teachers' loyalty TL. Moreover, the study showed that teachers' loyalty facilitated the association between EL and COC. The current research recommended that it was essential to increase the standard of ethical leadership EL for managers, to positively influence COC and to enhance TL.

Key Words: Ethical Leadership EL; Continuance Organizational Commitment Coc; Teachers' Loyalty TL.

1. Introduction

An ethical leader EL builds a positive environment by acting and taking decisions ethically in everyday interactions (Northouse, 2013). Ethical leadership EL is a contemporary area of study which has recently received much attention as a result of the positive effect that this leadership style has on employees and their organisations.

Loyalty means being committed to the prosperity of the organisation, having feelings of bonding with other members of the organisation, caring, and taking responsibility (Rajput, Singhal, & Tiwari, 2016). Ethical leadership EL not only fosters employees' loyalty, it also develops their sense of commitment towards the employing organisation, and acts as a point of strength for the individual's identification with, connection to, participation with, and assistance in the achievement of their organisation (Abdelhamid, 2017).

Many studies have examined the relationship between EL (Ethical leadership) - where the leader shows trust, dignity, honesty, and consideration toward employees - and employees' COC (continues organisational commitment). However, there is a dearth of such studies in the educational field of International Schools in KSA.

The implementation of research into Ethical leadership EL in a diverse range of contexts is essential to identify any obstacles, to the develop positive features identified, and to address any emerging challenges. However, school leaders should be qualified to practice leadership behaviors, that demonstrate the characteristics of an ethical leader, and to guide their schools effectively to face various challenges.

There is a lack of previous research into ethical leaders' behavior and its relation to: teachers' organisational

commitment, teacher's loyalty to supervisors in international schools, and the significance of this new approach to Saudi culture. Therefore, the research questions for the current study were as follows:

- 1) What is the relationship between the ethical style of leadership and teachers' organisational commitment?
- 2) What is the relationship between ethical styles of leadership and teachers' loyalty?
- 3) What is the mediation impact of teachers' loyalty and the perspectives of Ethical leadership EL on teachers' continuance organisational commitment COC?

2. Aims of the study:

- Expose the relationship between the perception of ethical leaders' behaviour and teachers' commitment toward their international schools.
- Expose the relationship between the perception of Ethical leadership EL and teachers' loyalty to their supervisors at the international schools.
- Examine the mediation effect of teachers' loyalty on the relationship between the perception of Ethical leadership EL and teachers' organisational commitment.

2.1. The importance of the study

Schools are considered to be social institutions that have structurally open systems of interaction with parents, teachers, and many other members of the society, therefore the implementation of Ethical leadership EL is crucial. Teachers and administrative staff in schools are guiding the next generation, and students spend a great deal of their time in schools where they will imitate their teachers' behavior, develop their identity and form loyalties (Langlois & Lapointe, 2009). The current research aims to explore the mediating component of loyalty in relation to Ethical leadership EL and teachers' continuance organisational commitment in the international schools in Jeddah. The research was conducted in a contemporary and diverse context, which is a relatively new phenomenon in Saudi culture. The culture of both

2.2. Hypothesis of the study

H1: There is a relationship between school directors' Ethical leadership EL behavior and teachers' continuance organisational commitment.

H2: There is a relationship between school directors' Ethical leadership EL behavior and teachers' loyalty.

H3: There is a relationship between teachers' loyalty and teachers' continuance organisational commitment.

H4: Teachers' loyalty intermediates the relationship between Ethical leadership EL behavior and teachers' continuance organisational commitment.

teachers and managers at the international schools are diverse, and there is a possibility that misconceptions of Ethical leadership EL may exist.

Perceptions of Ethical leadership EL have a significant impact on teachers' organisational commitment and loyalty to their supervisor, which will help to enhance their relationship with their supervisors and will also suggest a guideline for these managers to follow when interacting with the teaching staff. This will encourage a compatible and harmonious relationship between managers and teachers, that will in turn result in a comfortable working environment and an enhanced performance of the high school. The current study will encourage and open the door for future research into the scope of international education in KSA, and will justify further testing into those aspects that support the quality of the educational system at the international schools. The majority of the research into teachers' organisational commitment shows that some agents influence their commitment and loyalty (Ahluwalia & Preet, 2017; Ozdemir & Yirci, 2017). Leaders are identified as being the most significant agents affecting employees' organisational behavior, as they play a critical role in the employees' experience of work and are the main actors responsible for creating a relaxed and desirable working environment (Yirci, Ozdemir, Kartal, & Kocabaş, 2014).

The current study will help uncover critical areas in the Ethical leadership EL process that many researchers could not explore. Therefore, the study may provide a new view on leadership.

primacy of society, as international schools play an essential part in the educational system. The heightened demand for highly committed and loyal teachers at those schools justifies the search for more effective, life-changing approaches to management and leadership. Therefore, managers that apply the approach recommended by this research will be capable of generating greater levels of loyalty and commitment from their teachers. Managers and leaders should receive guidance on those aspects of their leadership styles that should be emphasized to improve both teachers' performance and their psychological connection to the organization.

The current study employed a descriptive approach due to the natural relationship between the variables of the study. The researcher used the Descriptive approach has proven useful in cases where researchers had little control over the situation or circumstances. Descriptive research has also been categorized as merely the effort to determine, define and recognize the situation (Ethridge, 2004). The Descriptive approach has been described as being "designed to cast light on current issues or problems through a procedure of data collection that enables us to describe the situation more completely than it was possible before using that method" (Fox & Bayat, 2007).

Brown et. al. (2005) described Ethical leadership EL as the demonstration, through individual actions and interpersonal relationships, of normatively correct behaviour, and the transference of such behaviour to followers via three routes: reinforcement, communication and decision making. Mai (2015) describes employees' organisational commitment as the harmonization of objective and values between the employee and the organisation, which fuels the desire of the employee to fulfill the goals of the organisation.

According to Marguita (2015), the loyalty of individual employees is described as the willing commitment to promote the benefits and agenda of the employer even when this requires the sacrifice of their own priorities, beyond the individual's legal and moral duties.

3. Literature review

3.1. Leadership

Leadership is a subject that generates interest worldwide and there exists much material, both general and academic, into leadership direction. However, despite the wealth of published studies into leadership, the topic of leadership behaviour has continued to mystify scientists and scholars of the field (Northouse, 2013). People with a firm belief in ethical values tend to demonstrate moral behaviors and attitudes. These values and attitudes are evident in their daily actions and interactions. Therefore, ethical behavior is controlled by one's values and the principles that one grew up with (Agal, 2017).

Leadership concepts developed rapidly at the beginning of the last century. They were thoroughly studied and defined by many philosophers over this period, and each one has identified leadership from his own perspective. Put simply, leadership means guiding people or groups to fulfill a specific set of objectives. Northouse (2013) has defined leadership as "a procedure whereby an individual affects a group of individuals to achieve a common goal". While Cohen (1990) described it as "to do with having things completed and fulfilled by acting through others". Leadership is the process of influencing an individuals or teams to fulfill a common goal (Cemberci, Civelek & Gunel, 2016). The term leadership was defined by Timm & Peterson (1982) as "the term we apply to the movers and shakers of this world - the men and women who have the amazing power to get others to do things."

Leadership is the capability to influence others, particularly in compelling others to reach challenging goals. Some leaders use their charisma and attraction, while for others desire and excitation are their primary tools. Other leaders may use their vast knowledge base and intelligence, whilst for others strength and courageousness can be the method through which they influence followers (Chapman & O'Neil, 1999).

Northouse (2013) and Cemberci et al. (2016) agreed that leadership is an influencing process that helps to guide people to reach goals. Cohen (1990) determined that leadership is a means of achieving goals. Whilst Timm & Peterson (1982) viewed leadership as the exclusive power that changes people, Chapman & O'Neil (1999) described leadership as a skill or ability present in some people that attracts and influences others. The over-arching aim of leadership - to reach and achieve an accomplishment or set of accomplishments - is the one area of agreement amongst researchers. Therefore, the process of leadership can be defined as inspiring individuals to facilitate tasks and attain goals.

Great leaders are good listeners and followers. One of their most important traits is listening to people, as this helps them to internalise good advice. Leadership involves tolerance and can also be guided by passion. A good leader knows when it is time to let others celebrate their success. He/she also knows what values are essential to enable a group to carry loads, burdens, and responsibilities as a team. Great leaders spend a great deal of time thinking, and they mobilise the strength of other people (Stuckelberger, Fust & Ike, 2016).

There are several styles of leadership that have been the focus of much research throughout the years. Some of those styles feature servant leaders who place followers' rights as their priority and place emphasis on followers' growth (Hale & Fields, 2007). The trait approach viewed leadership as an inherent set of attributes and characteristics displayed by an individual, including confidence, responsibility, and intelligence (Hogan, p.334, 2005). Bass and Stogdill (1990) suggest that a skilled approach to leadership is based on leaders' knowledge and their competency in organising the organisation's objectives. A transformational leader is one who exhibits leadership behaviour through raising peoples' motivation and moral (Bass, p.431, 1995). The perspective of Ethical leadership EL has developed in the twentieth century as a direct result of the financial scandals of some of the international companies. Brown et al. (2005) described the Ethical leader as one who will establish "two-way communication" with his followers through interpersonal relationships, encouraging participation in decision making and - as it is important to direct the organisation's plans and attain their primary aims - engaging the followers in organisational actions, (Kanungo & Mendonca, 1996). In light of this, Ethical leadership EL has postulated upon instructions and values that may assist leadership of the organization (Starratt, 2004). Ethical practice in government or any agency provides the prerequisite for creating the right policy decisions and applying the rules (Okechukwu, 2012). Ethical leadership EL is an essential component of the morality that affects the beliefs, values, behavior, and thoughts of leaders, and a study of Ethical leadership EL would benefit the organisational leadership (Serrano, 2016).

Ethical leaders differentiate themselves by demonstrating qualities that are consistent with basic ethical principles such as honesty, fairness, and trustworthiness, and balanced decision-making (Okana & Akyuzb, 2016). Ethical leadership EL starts with the leaders and progressively includes many groups in the society. Therefore, ethical leaders have many responsibilities; they are responsible to themselves as they more than anybody should align to ethical principles, they are responsible for the organisation as they must enforce ethical rules and social responsibility, and they must introduce these principles to the public (Ozdemir & Yirci, 2017). Ethical leaders in business are defined by Lam (2016) as the ones who bring obvious ethical consequences, regardless of their internal motivations. Being a moral leader is significant as there is something about ethical behaviour that makes it fundamentally virtuous and not driven by reasons of self-interest (Lam, 2016). Ethical leadership EL essentially emphasizes appropriate conduct not just for those who lead but also for the whole organization (Okechukwu, 2012). There are many reasons to encourage the adaptation of Ethical leadership EL in today's organizations.

Ethical behavior is important to long-term success, and conversely, unethical behavior leads to a decrease in long-term performance (Fritzsche, 2005). Being ethical is essential, and it is required in all level of organisations, especially for those leaders who act as role models to their employees. Ethical leadership EL is a model for ethical conduct to the organization and to society, as leaders are the role-models for the employees in those groups. EL (Ethical leadership) builds trust, as people will follow a moral leader because they know they can trust him to take the right action as he sees it (Stuckelberger, Fust, & Ike, 2016).

EL (Ethical leadership) brings trustworthiness and respect for the leader themselves and also for the organisation, as the integrity of the ethical leader earns the respect of individuals and groups both within the organisation and outside it. EL (Ethical leadership) leads to improved cooperation with other organisations, as these bodies will be much more willing to work in partnership when they know that your dealings are ethical. EL (Ethical leadership) creates a healthy atmosphere within the staff group, as employees are likely to feel more protected, and more dedicated to the organisation. EL (Ethical leadership) affords the leader a sense of self-respect, as he consistently considers the ethics of his decisions, actions, and interactions, and does not have to question his own integrity (Stuckelberger, Fust, & Ike, 2016). The distinguishing feature of EL (Ethical leadership) that sets it apart from other theories of leadership is the transactional-style management of the ethics and behavior of the organisation. Ethical leaders are proactive in sustaining ethical conduct amongst their staff (Crews, 2011).

It could be that the possession of specific characteristics may predispose an individual to an ethical style of

leadership. Certainly, ethical leaders identify with and value such traits as kindness, honesty, truthfulness, and fairness, and the presence of these traits is considered necessary for the leader to achieve credibility and effectiveness. In contrast, narcissistic, pseudo-authentic, personalized charismatic and destructive leadership are characteristics associated with un Ethical leadership (Crews, 2011). Ethical leaders lead by example; they can develop connections, impose ethics, and improve practice standards in organisations. The ethical leaders' manner and decisions are grounded in ethical values, meaning that their followers also seek to demonstrate nobility in their actions and decisions to consolidate the common morale (Okechukwu, 2012).

As Ethical leadership EL is new concept that only emerged this century, it offers numerous opportunities for a rich variety of research projects, and the chance for researchers to reach new informational horizons. Ethical leaders have a substantial influence on their employees, thus enhancing the employees' loyalty, which is the mediator of continuance organisational commitment in this research study. Loyalty in organisations is important as it has an impact on employees' performance and engagement. The standard and style of leadership will influence the degree of loyalty demonstrated by staff within those organisations. The use of Ethical leadership EL in organisations will have a positive effect on the levels of employee loyalty. Leaders who are honest, who give advice to employees, care for them, and treat them fairly, will receive obedience and loyalty in return.

According to Mathieu & Zajac (1990), loyalty is seen as an organisational bond that may be deemed a psychological response - an employee who has a strong belief in organisational values will place a greater insistence on attaining organisational goals.

Loyalty also represents a psychological state, in terms of employees' relationship with the organisation, which has implications for their decision about whether or not to remain at the organisation (Allen & Grisaffe, 2001). Consequently, loyalty is identified as the instinctive urge to remain connected to the organisation, which has a significant role in staff retention. Employee loyalty can be recognised as a feeling of attachment to the organisation, which evolves as a result of the high standard of job satisfaction. These psychological emotions develop into the employees' attitude towards the organisation.

Therefore, the greater the satisfaction of the employee with their working environment, the higher their loyalty and commitment to the organisation (Rajput, Singhal, & Tiwari, 2016). Some companies have highly loyal employees, who may become resistant to future change. Their deep attachment to the values of the organisation may result in them becoming frightened about planned changes that may affect the company. On the contrary, employees who are less committed to the organisation may follow with the proposed amendments more easily

as they are not sufficiently invested in the destiny of the organisation to resist the changes (Robbins & Judge, 2012). Chaubey (2014) described employees' loyalty as the quality of being truthful to others or to organisations. Similarly, Norman & Wu (2006) identified employees' organisational loyalty as a strong association between employees and their employer, resulting in the creation of a positive bond with the organization (Mehta, Bhakar & Sikarwar, 2010).

The notion of loyalty has been loosely defined, and the literature is inconclusive on the difference between commitment and loyalty. Commitment to an organization is an individual decision about whether to commit or not based on sound judgment. Whereas loyalty encompasses a normative component – namely, that it is a responsibility or duty. Commitment is unidirectional, whereas loyalty arises out of relationships and is reciprocated (Nagra & S, 2011). To earn the loyalty of one's employees' is considered to be the ultimate goal of the leader-follower relationship (Kanungo & Mendonca, 1996). Gaining loyalty necessitates several actions. Nowadays attitudes have changed, as salary and competitive benefits are not the only means of earning employees' loyalty. Obtaining loyalty by giving high salaries has shown to be a short-run motivator, so the more diligent managers are employing to non-financial rewards to motivate employees, such increasing the positive ambiances of the working environment (Klopotan, Buntak & Drożdżek, 2015). As a result, employees are very focused on working in a healthy environment, on the ethical standards of their leaders and on how they are treated by the leaders, which is the focus of this study.

The stereotype of employment loyalty had been transformed by the increase in globalization, where employees have been subjected to reorganization, company replacements and downsizing. In this process, employers broke with tradition, mutual commitments were reevaluated, lifetime job security and dedication became less certain, job-hopping became the norm, and people became motivated by competitive salaries or a better working environment (Mehta, Bhakar, & Sikarwar, 2010).

According to Mehta, Bhakar, & Sikarwar (2010), loyalty has two dimensions, internal and external. Loyalty is primarily an emotional attachment. The internal dimension includes the feelings of consideration, of connection and commitment. This dimension has to be fostered and attracted. The external dimension relates to the means by which loyalty reveals itself. This dimension is expressed in the mannerisms that express the emotional components, and it is the most changeable aspect of loyalty. Therefore, the definition of loyalty should be refined as: those internal emotions that may be expressed in a variety of contemporary and emerging behaviours.

Narteh and Odoom (2015) suggest that dedicated, loyal employees will possess high levels of motivation, and

are more likely to conduct themselves and to perform in a manner that benefits the organisation, Thus, maintaining employee's loyalty is important for the prosperity and endurance of the organisation.

Modern concepts of loyalty differ greatly from those of the past. Instead of visionless corporate obedience, employees display their commitment to their hard work for the organisation. The sooner that organisations realise that they have to make numerous efforts to gain employee loyalty, the more successful they will be at employing and maintaining the best and the brightest staff. Several studies show that corporate and shareholder return on investment is directly associated with employee retention rates. The organizations that selected the best companies working worldwide are almost those are which perform better than others (Mehta, Bhakar, & Sikarwar, 2010).

Loyal employees develop a life-long relationship with their organisation, which results in organisational commitment - the other variable of our research study.

3.2. Continuance organizational commitment

Organisational commitment is considered to be an organisational outcome, and one which researchers have focused on recently. Every organisation wants staff that have a passion for the organisation's mission and objectives, staff who – even in the absence of a leader - would represent their organisation in a way that would enhance its reputation. Organizations also want staff who are keen to remain in the organisation, as this goes a long way towards determining the continuity of the organisation. Teams are the life-blood of every organisation, and their attitude towards the organisation is a requirement of its productivity and sustainability (Daniel & Eze, 2016). Organisational commitment is acknowledged to be an indicator of the level of affiliation that the employee has attained with organisation (Robbins & Judge, 2012). It is a psychological agreement that connects employees to their organisation and decreases the level of staff turnover (Allen & Meyer, 1990). Organisational commitment is linked to turnover; employees who have a high standard of commitment to their organisations are less likely to quit, while staff who are less committed are indicative of a high turnover rate. Organizational commitment includes three aspects or attributes: influential, continuance, and normative commitment (Allen & Meyer, 1990).

An effective engagement is identified via the degree to which employees are spiritually and emotionally associated to, recognised by and are engaged with the organisation. Mitonga-Monga & Cilliers (2016) observed connections between Ethical leadership in and employees' organisational commitment in an organisation in the Democratic Republic of Congo. Individuals continue in their job when they have a passion for the career, which makes them not want to quit. They place less value on financial remuneration

for their work, but and greater value on the love they possess for the profession. The positive outcome of affective commitment is that the staff remain with the organisation as they 'want to.' They have arranged their role at the organisation as part of their everyday lives, and this has formed a connection between them and the firm (Daniel & Eze, 2016).

Mitonga-Monga and Cilliers (2016) define continuance commitment as the degree to which employees wish and intentionally accede to stay with an organisation. They suggest that staff who display continuance commitment have invested expressively, physically and intellectually in the organisation, and find the thought of leaving unpalatable.

Continuance commitment is also identified as “the attachment employees have towards their organization as there is a perceived belief that there is a high cost associated with losing their membership in the organization. It also considers the nature of the economy as well as the social cost of living” (Daniel & Eze, 2016). In other words, staff who have the highest standards of continuance commitment remain in the organization, as they feel that they need to do so (Daniel & Eze, 2016).

Several researchers, including Mitonga-Monga and Cilliers (2016) and Gill et. al. (2011), have described normative commitment as the extent to which employees feel a sense of compulsion to remain with an organisation, believing that it is morally right to remain in the organisation. Researchers suggest that normative and substantial commitment have a similar relativity to the outcome variables. However, affective commitment tends to have stronger ties in comparison to continuance commitment, which is weakly or negatively correlated to workplace outcomes. Continuance organizational commitment COC is considered to be the independent variable in the current study, and according to McGee & Ford (1987) it involves two dimensions. The first is a low alternative, requiring commitment due to the lack of other professional opportunities. The second is high sacrifice, which involves the associations of loss of investments with withdrawal from the organization (Taing, Granger, Groff, Jackson, & Johns, 2011).

Vandenberghe, Panaccio, & Ben Ayed (2011) proposed that continuance sacrifices commitment makes the thought of having to transfer to another firm a troubling possibility, and continuance alternatives commitment makes the experience of remaining with the organization pleasurable.

Hrebiniak & Alutto (1972) take a calculative approach to their view of continuance commitment, suggesting that the accumulation of interests and external rewards motivate an individual to remain with an organisation. Therefore, as Carson & Carson (2002) suggest, the connection can be viewed as a tendency to continue one's commitment to the organisation due to the personal sacrifice associated with leaving and a lack of alternatives.

In the current study, Ethical leadership EL is assessed through the mediator of variable loyalty, that works as an aid to help employees reach a high standard of commitment toward their organisation. Many studies have been conducted into the relationship between the variables; ethical leadership, continuance organizational commitment COC, and employees' loyalty. Neubert, Wu, & Roberts (2013) have confirmed that ethical leaders encourage employees' commitment and organisational behavior. Leaders are the ones who are responsible for shaping their employees' attitudes. Okana & Akyuz (2015) also confirmed, in their mediator analysis study of higher-education staff and academics, that Ethical leadership has a notable impact on employee's job satisfaction, while employee loyalty acts as a full mediator in such relationships. Another study (Shin, Sung & Choi, 2015), that examined the impact of Ethical leadership of top management on the performance in Korean employees, showed that the ethical conduct of higher managers helps to promote an ethical climate, which enhances the organisation's performance.

Qianqian, Biyan, Qian, Sinian & Mengshi (2014) held a study in the Chinese hospitality industry to inspect the consequence of Ethical leadership on employees' engagement with the mediator of job satisfaction, and the outcome demonstrated a considerable effect of Ethical leadership on employee engagement and attitude.

Zdemir & Yirci (2017) tested the relationship between Ethical leadership and an encouraging school climate among teachers, with the results demonstrating a significant positive relationship between the schoolmasters' Ethical leadership standards and positive ambiance practices.

Tosun & Ulusoy (2017) conducted a study to analyse organisational commitment among doctors' and nurses', satisfaction and the level of burnout in a Turkish hospital. They concluded that as emotional commitment, normative commitment and technical achievement were increased, and while the continuation commitment level increases, the vocational satisfaction level decreases. Markovits (2012) investigated the impact of job satisfaction and continuance commitment on organisational citizenship conducted within employees from private and public organisations in Greece. Markovits discovered an interactive influence amongst continuance commitment, job satisfaction, and organizational citizenship conduct for both divisions. Also, within this relationship, the role of job satisfaction is to explain when this relationship is active and in what direction. Therefore, when job satisfaction is low, increasing standards of continuance commitment result in decreasing standards of organisational citizenship conduct, while whenever job satisfaction is high, rising levels of continuance commitment increase organisational citizenship conduct.

Rajput, Singhal, & Tiwari (2016) explored the influence of job satisfaction on employees' loyalty in academicians to establish the various factors implicit in job satisfaction and employees' loyalty. They found that job satisfaction had a critical impact on employee loyalty among academicians. The implicit operators of job satisfaction that emerged from this study are career growth, motivation, workplace environment, and self-satisfaction. While the implicit factors of employees' loyalty are belongingness, job involvement, and organizational commitment.

There is a lack of research into the effect of Ethical leadership EL on continuance organizational commitment with the mediate of employees' loyalty.

3.3. The conceptual framework:

The theoretical framework of the current research consists of three variables; ethical leadership, organizational commitment, and loyalty. Ethical leadership styles which involve being fair, trusting of, honest to and respectful of followers can lead to the development of a positive environment, lifelong relationships, and employees' loyalty. Therefore, employees' loyalty and the strong bond or correlation to the organisation leads employees to insist on remaining in their organisation, which matures into continuance commitment. This study will explore the impact of Ethical leadership on teachers' continuance organisational commitment with the mediator variable of teachers' loyalty.

Prior studies have been conducted in relation to leaders' behavior, style and characteristics, and each study has approached the concept of leadership from different perspectives, leading to differing results.

Okana & Akyuzb (2016) conducted a study to examine the mediating role of loyalty to one's supervisor on the relationship of Ethical leadership and job satisfaction among the academic and administrative staff of Gumuhane University in Turkey. The results showed that ethical leaders' behavior is influential on loyalty to a supervisor, which causes an increase in employees' job satisfaction. It confirmed that there is specific role of supervisors' loyalty in the relationship between Ethical leadership and employees' job satisfaction.

Eslamieh & Davoudi (2016) conducted research and examined the relationship between ethical leadership, organisational commitment, and burnout in secondary school teachers. The study showed that there is a definite relationship between Ethical leadership and corporate commitment, and a negative relationship with exhaustion. As managers are the official representatives of the organisations, with the most prominent role in coordination and increasing productivity of the organisations, their effective management and implementation of appropriate leadership styles is highly influential on whether or not the organisation develops, prospers and reach its goals. Ethical leadership styles also affect the teacher's attitude,

behavior, and emotions in a positive way, which leads to high job satisfaction and low rates of burnout.

Cemberci et. al. (2016) examined the mediator role of the ethical climate on the relationship between Ethical leadership and organisational commitment in different companies operating in various sectors in Istanbul. The results showed that ethical conduct by a leader was not sufficient to elicit organisational commitment unless the leader had first created an ethical climate. Employees who work in organisations with ethical organisational environments have a high standard of responsibility compared to employees working in unethical environments.

Monga's (2016) study has aimed to determine the relationship between Ethical leadership and organisational commitment in a railway organisation in the Democratic Republic of the Congo. The results highlighted that Ethical leadership has a considerable impact on the standard of organisational commitment. The research further showed that Ethical leadership predicted employees' effective, continuation, normative and above all commitment. These outcomes add new insights into the structure of business ethics by showing that employees' genuine understanding of Ethical leadership is a significant factor in reinforcing their organizational commitment.

The study of Katranci et. al (2015) at vocational high schools in Turkey, examined the teachers' perceptions of the Principals' Ethical leadership conduct. The findings demonstrated that, firstly, teachers were confident that the Principals demonstrated Ethical leadership conduct and, secondly, that the teachers approved of such conduct. The study also found that certain demographical characteristics of the teachers had a positive impact on the teachers' perceptions and views of the principals' Ethical leadership conduct. These demographical factors included: gender, subject taught, school type and professional seniority. In addition, the study revealed that there were meaningful distinctions between the teachers' perceptions of Ethical leadership conduct based on some of these demographic factors, including school type, professional seniority, gender, subject, and period of service at the school. Thus, private variables could be viewed as influencing agents in the formation of the teachers' perceptions.

Celik, Dedeoglu & Inanir (2015) tested the partial mediator effect of organisational commitment on the relationship between Ethical leadership and job satisfaction in the employees of four and five-star hotels. The results showed that the impact of Ethical leadership on job satisfaction is quite small. However, when organisational commitment and Ethical leadership are integrated, leaders who act ethically cause employees to become more satisfied with their jobs by reinforcing organisational commitment.

Yang's (2014) study examined the moderating influence of job satisfaction on Ethical leadership and life satisfaction of workers in Taiwan. The outcome

revealed that leadership has a powerful effect on employees' job satisfaction, which positively reflects the subordinates' well-being and life satisfaction. Communication between managers and subordinates is encouraged; it creates an appropriate working environment and increases job satisfaction. Therefore, employees' well-being and life satisfaction increase as they transfer the positive emotions and feelings experienced at work into other areas of their lives.

Research carried out by Qianqian, Biyan, Qian, Sinian, & Mengshi (2014) examined the impact of EL (Ethical leadership) on employee work attitudes and behaviors, and the partially moderating impact of job satisfaction and work engagement at the hotels in China. The outcomes of the research showed that employees' job satisfaction and work engagement were indicative of the impact of the ethical leaders' behavior on employee's customer-oriented behavior. Ethical leadership can generate positive outputs through increasing employees' job satisfaction and engagement, which conferred a competitive advantage to the organisation that supports the external effects and enhances customer satisfaction. In addition, employees' work engagement in the area of deep appreciation plays a significant role in improving both employees' behavior toward customers and their job satisfaction. However, as yet, employees' engagement has received comparatively little attention from scholars. Furthermore, Peggy & Siegel (2013) conducted research to determine the predictors and outcomes of ethical leaders' behavior and organizational commitment. The study examined the relationship between these variables on a sample of members of the Canadian Armed Forces. The results revealed that supervisors' Ethical leadership had a direct and positive relationship with the influential and standard commitment of employees, moreover, both male and female supervisors exhibited similar Ethical leadership behaviors.

4. Research Methodology:

The study methodology is a process that includes methods and techniques that the study uses to accomplish its objectives. That means the research methodology could describe a previously-designed strategy which researchers follow to reach their conclusions. When the researcher determines the research problem, he must seek out a solution for the entire problem. Therefore, the data collection tools employed should be clearly identified as able to yield data that will achieve the study objectives. The researcher must carefully plan all aspects of data collection, including specific documents to be used, specifying parameters for the sample population, and choosing the correct techniques by which to analyse the collected data.

As stated by Kothari (2004), the study methodology is a method to fix the problem the study assumes systematically. Moreover, it can be realized as a

science of examining how research is carried out scientifically, and the reasoning supporting that. Harvey Maylor & Kate Blackmon (2005) argued that research methodology is the description of the translation research perspective into a form of studying the world. A research methodology may be implemented through various study designs, the outline of conducting the study, through translating the study methodology into specific research methods, and the techniques used to get and analyze data.

In research methodology, researchers adopt a number of approaches, separated into two broad categories: the quantitative and qualitative approaches.

The current study employed the descriptive approach to demonstrate the natural relationship between the variables of the study, and to test the study hypothesis. The descriptive approach has frequently used by researchers of the social and humane sciences (Ozdemir & Yirci, 2017).

The study population in the current research includes all teachers of the International Schools in Jeddah city in the west region of KSA. The research population includes male and female teachers of all grades; the number of female teachers is 5241, while that of male teachers is 1904.

4.1. Sample:

The sample size in the current study was decided based on the use of statistical table techniques to represent the population, by using the mathematical established table for a random sample established by Krecie & Morgan (1970), and the 95.00% dependability grade was taken into consideration. Therefore, according to the table, which was developed from a mathematical formula, when considering the appropriate size of a random sample for a given population of 7145 teachers, the sample size that best represents the study population is 364 teachers (Cohen, 2007, P: 102).

4.2. Methods:

In the current research, a questionnaire is used as a technique for data collection. That consists of two forms of variables. Sample demographic characteristics include: gender, education level, years of experience, and school location in Jeddah city. The other types of variables are the primary variables of the research, namely: Ethical leadership EL as an independent variable in the study, teachers' organizational commitment COC as dependent variables, and teachers' loyalty TL which works as a mediator.

4.3. Validity and reliability:

The researcher applied a correlation relationship to test the validity of the association between the scales' sub item and the whole score of the measurement in the questionnaire to which it belongs. The outcomes are displayed in the upcoming table :

Table (1)**Correlation relationship between the questioner statement items**

No.	EL	COC		TL	
	Correlation coefficient	No. of item	Correlation coefficient	No. of item	Correlation coefficient
1	0.768**	11	0.259**	19	0.697**
2	0.702**	12	0.473**	20	0.823**
3	0.857**	13	0.577**	21	0.871**
4	0.427**	14	0.055	22	0.809**
5	0.876**	15	0.713**		
6	0.842**	16	0.733**		
7	0.662**	17	0.698**		
8	0.879**	18	0.590**		
9	0.869**				
10	0.728**				

** Indicated that the correlation coefficient is considerable at the (0.01) significance level.

The results showed that each statement item was statistically correlated with the aggregate score of the dimension, as the values lie between 0.259 to 0.876, these values are statistically valid at the 0.01 level of significance. Thus, these results proved that the questionnaire tool used for collecting data was valid, and all statement items measure what they were intended to measure.

4.4. Questionnaire reliability :

The researchers used two commonly-used techniques to inspect the questionnaire reliability, to be confident that the questionnaire would gather the data efficiently. The first method was to measure Alpha Cronbach's coefficient for each dimension item, and all questionnaire items, while the second method was to use the split-half technique, through applying Person's correlation coefficient and Spearman's correlation coefficient.

The statistics in showed that the Ethical leadership EL scale has reached 0.921, the organizational commitment COC scale has reached 0.611, and teachers' loyalty TL has reached 0.811, and showed that the overall survey technique had achieved very high reliability as the rate of Alpha Cronbach's coefficient reached 0.810 at the significance level 0.01. This confirms the reliability of the questionnaire and suggests that the questionnaire technique would be efficient in gathering the data needed on every occasion that it was distributed to the members of the intended research sample.

5. Data analysis

The results indicated that the study sample profile includes four demographic characteristics: gender, education level, years of experience, and school location. The female teachers of the international schools comprised the majority of the research participants, at 87.1%, whereas the male teachers represented just 12.9% of the research participants. Therefore, these results may reflect the fact that the researcher found it easier to contact female teachers than male teachers.

The study results indicated that 73.1% of the teachers hold a bachelor's degree, while 17.2% had a master's degree and 9.7% had a high school diploma. Therefore, the majority of teachers participating in the study are well educated, would thus be expected to understand the effect of leadership perception adopted in these schools on their continuance organizational commitment and their loyalty to the schools.

The research findings showed that more than half of the participants had worked at their school for over seven years, while 19.4% stated their teaching experience as being between 5-7 years. 15.3% had teaching experience of 1-3 years, and 14.5% between 3-5 years teaching experience.

The results demonstrated that the teachers according to the location of the school. It was observed that: 37.1% of the schools are located in the north of Jeddah, 27.7% of the schools are located in central Jeddah, 13.7% of the schools are located in west Jeddah, 11.8% are located in south Jeddah, and 9.7% of the schools are located in east Jeddah.

Descriptive statistical tools such as mean and standard deviation were used to estimate the participants' answers for each statement. It was found that participant's perspective about supervisor's Ethical leadership EL behavior amounted to 3.87, with scale deviation amounting to 0.72, meaning that a considerable number of participants perceived that their supervisors in the international schools display Ethical leadership EL behavior.

The responses of the participant teachers regarding their organisational commitment COC in the international schools in Jeddah revealed that the overall mean value reached 3.29, with standard deviation amounting to 0.65. This indicated that although some teachers are highly committed to the organisation, this level of commitment is not common amongst all teachers.

Teachers' responses for teachers' loyalty TL to their international schools in Jeddah revealed that the overall mean value reached 3.53, with deviation level equal to 0.90. Which demonstrated that a significant number of teachers agreed they have some loyalty to their current organisation?

Table (2)

Results of analysis of variance (ANOVA) to examine variations in participants' attitudes regarding Ethical leadership EL, continuance organizational commitment COC and Teachers' loyalty TL related to education level.

	Source of variation	Sum of squares	d.f	Mean sum of squares	F	Sig
EL	Between groups	2.337	2	1.168	2.29	0.10
	Within groups	188.291	369	0.510		
	Total	190.628	371			
COC	Between groups	2.874	2	1.437	3.447*	0.03
	Within groups	153.836	369	0.417		
	Total	156.710	371			
TL	Between groups	2.712	2	1.356	1.662	0.19
	Within groups	301.116	369	0.816		
	Total	303.829	371			

The tabulated F-test statistics was calculated at df (2, 369) and significance level (0.05) is equal to (3.00).

The outcomes of the analysis of variances in the above table indicated that there is a statistically important difference between sample perceptions concerning continuance organisational commitment COC in the international schools in Jeddah, related to education level at the significance level 0.05. In contrast, the results do not indicate any remarkable distinction between teachers' ethical leadership EL, and teachers' loyalty TL.

To examine to which education level the significant differences regarding continuance organizational commitment COC exist, a multiple comparison analysis was conducted by using the L.S.D (Least Square difference) method.

Table (3)

The results of multiple comparison analysis with regard to continuance organizational commitment COC by education level

Comparison means of education levels/ COC			
High school diploma	-	0.293*	0.311*
Bachelor	-0.293*	-	-
Masters	-0.311*	-	-

The outcomes in the above table revealed that the notable differences between participants' responses regarding continuance organisational commitment COC related to education level exist between participants who hold a high school diploma, compared with those whose education level is a bachelor's and masters' degree ($F=3.447^*$, $p<0.05$). This means that participants with lower educational levels are more committed to their organization COC .

Table (4)

The results of analysis of variance (ANOVA) to test variations in participants' attitudes regarding Ethical leadership EL, continuance organizational commitment COC and Teachers' loyalty TL related to years of experience.

	Source of variation	Sum of squares	d.f	Mean sum of squares	F	Sig
EL	Between groups	3.071	3	1.024	2.008	0.11
	Within groups	187.557	368	0.510		
	Total	190.628	371			
COC	Between groups	5.082	3	1.694	4.11**	0.007
	Within groups	151.628	368	0.412		
	Total	156.170	371			
TL	Between groups	25.054	3	8.351	11.024**	0.00
	Within groups	278.774	368	0.758		
	Total	303.829	371			

**indicated that the difference is significant at the (0.01) significance level. The tabulated F-test statistics was calculated at df (3, 368) and significance level (0.05) is equal to (2.60)

The outcomes of variance analysis in the above table demonstrate that there is a significant difference between teachers' perception regarding ethical leadership, continuance organisational commitment COC, and teachers' loyalty TL in the international schools in Jeddah. It is related to years of experience at the significance level 0.01. The results did not show any unusual distinction between teachers' perceptions of ethical leadership EL.

A multiple comparison analysis was conducted, to determine to which years of experience these significant differences exist, and the outcomes are displayed in the upcoming table :

Table (5)

The results of multiple comparison analysis regarding continuance organisational commitment COC by years of experience

Years of experience		Mean differences			
		1-to less than 3	3-to less than 5	5-to less than 7	More than 7
COC	1-to less than 3				0.278*
	3-to less than 5				0.260*
	5-to less than 7				
	More than 7	-0.278*	-0.260*		
TL	1-to less than 3			-0.713*	-0.576*
	3-to less than 5			-0.583*	-0.446*
	5-to less than 7	0.713*	0.583*		
	More than 7	0.576*	0.446*		

*indicated that the mean difference is significant at the (0.05) significance level.

Concerning continuance organisational commitment COC, the mean difference related to years of experience exists between teachers whose years of experience number between 1 to less than 3, and 3 to less than 5 years, as compared to those with more than seven years' experience, and it was favorable to the benefit of the first two groups.

The mean differences of teachers' loyalty TL among participants whose years of experience was between 5 to less than 7 years, and those whose years of experience numbered between 1 to less than 3 years, and 3 to less than 5 years. Also, the distinction is considerable between participants with experience of more than seven years compared to those with years of experience between 1 to less than 3 years, and between 3 to less than 5, and it is positive to the final two years of experience .

Person's correlation coefficient was employed to inspect the connection between research variables. It

was found that the correlation coefficient between Ethical leadership EL dimensions and teachers' continuance organisational commitment COC reached 0.003, which is insignificant as the significance level is greater than 0.05. The Ethical leadership EL has no considerable impact on school teachers' organisational commitment COC.

However, the correlation coefficient value between Ethical leadership EL and teachers' loyalty TL to their organisations are statistically significant, reaching 0.405 at the significance level 0.01. Therefore, there is significance to the amount of teachers' loyalty produced by ethical leadership EL.

To test hypothesis Three, the four steps of regression analysis were conducted:

Step1- Carry out a simple regression analysis with Ethical leadership EL on organisational commitment COC, path (c).

The result declared that there is no considerable impact of Ethical leadership EL on organizational commitment COC ($\beta=0.002$, $p<0.05$, n.s.). This means that the two variables Ethical leadership EL and organizational commitment COC were not related, so the results do not support H1 which stated that "There is a relationship between school directors' Ethical leadership behavior and teachers' continuance organisational commitment." Based on Shrout & Bolger (2002), the significance of the association between dependent and independent variables should not be a requirement of mediational steps, when there is a priori belief of such relationship that the effect sample size is small. Also, Taylor & Mackinnon (2008) have proved that if the significant relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variables does not exist, the mediation effect may occur.

Figure 1: The hypothesised model

Step 2: conduct a simple regression analysis of Ethical leadership EL on teachers' loyalty TL to test for the path (a), meaning that there is a direct association from Ethical leadership EL to teacher's loyalty TL.

The findings show there is a considerable impact of Ethical leadership EL on teachers' loyalty TL ($\beta=0.205$, $p<0.00$), meaning that Ethical leadership EL is able to predict teachers' loyalty TL, as 0.405 of changes in Ethical leadership EL is caused by teachers' loyalty TL. Accordingly, the results support H2 which stated that "There is a relationship between school directors' Ethical leadership behavior and teachers' loyalty".

Step 3: conduct a simple regression analysis of teachers' loyalty on organisational commitment to test the significance of path (b).

Therefore, it could be comprehended that there is a significant direct effect of the mediator teachers' loyalty TL on continuous organisational commitment COC, ($\beta=0.07$, $p<0.05$). Accordingly, the results support H3, which stated that "There is a relationship between teachers' loyalty and teachers' continuance organisational commitment".

Step 4: conducting a path analysis by Amos software to test the mediational impact of teachers' loyalty on the relationship between TL ethical leadership EL and continuous organisational commitment COC.

The results of the test supported H4, which stated: Teachers' loyalty intermediates the relationship between Ethical leadership behavior and teachers' continuance organisational commitment.

Following this, a Sobel test was run to examine the indirect relationship, which produced a statistically significant value of Z ($Z= 2.04$, $p <0.05^*$) using Preacher and Hayes's online calculator (2008). It suggests that there is an indirect connection between Ethical leadership EL and continuous organisational commitment COC, that has been transmitted by teachers' loyalty TL ($Z= 2.04$, $p <0.05^*$). Thus, the results confirmed that teachers' loyalty TL has a mediational effect on the relationship between Ethical leadership EL and continuous organisational commitment COC, and based on this result, H4 is confirmed.

Figure2: Teacher's loyalty TL as a mediator between Ethical leadership EL and continuous organisational commitment COC.

Moreover, there is evidence of a full mediational effect for teachers' loyalty TL on ethical leaders' behavior and continuous organisational commitment COC, so the direct consequence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, after adding the mediator, is not significant ($\beta = -.032$, n.s.). This means there is full mediation effect between Ethical leadership EL and continuance organisational commitment COC transmitted through teachers' loyalty. Teachers' loyalty TL would increase teachers' continuance organisational commitment COC.

6. Discussion

The current study found that the supervisors in the international schools exhibited Ethical leadership EL behavior, which had an influence on teachers' work. This accorded with the findings of Qianqian, Biyan, Qian, Sinian & Mengshi (2014), that when Ethical leadership EL increases, employee job satisfaction and engagement are also increased. In addition, the current study confirmed the outcomes of Celik, Dedeoglu, & Inanir (2015) which demonstrated the partial mediation effect of organisational commitment on the relationship between Ethical leadership and job satisfaction among hotel employees. The results of the current study agree with previous studies in several ways, as they conclude that ethical leaders have various positive effects on teachers' commitment in the international school in Jeddah. Among these positive effects are the actions of supervisors who encourage teachers by carefully listening to them, and discussing the schools' ethics and values with them, which in turn contributes to the teachers improving their commitment to their school. Furthermore, the current study agreed with the finding of Katranci, Sungu, & Saglam (2015) which investigated the teachers' perceptions about their principals' Ethical leadership EL in vocational high schools. It revealed that teachers approved of the principals' exhibition of Ethical leadership behaviours, and the teachers viewed the ethical leaders' values favorably. Similarly, as our study showed, when the supervisors discuss the schools' ethics and values with the teachers, this encourages the teachers to become more loyal. One of the main findings of this study has demonstrated that the significant relationship between Ethical leadership EL and teachers' continuance commitment COC has diminished. This means that Ethical leadership EL styles had no significant effect on teachers' organisational commitment COC in the schools that were the focus of the current study. Similarly, the current findings agreed with the findings of Cimerci, Civelek, & Gunel (2016), which tested the mediator role of the ethical climate on the relationship between Ethical leadership EL and organisational commitment in different Turkish companies. The study showed that ethical actions by a leader are not sufficient to generate organisational commitment unless the leader first creates an ethical climate. Furthermore, the findings were supported by Siegel's (2013) results, in which he found that the perception of Ethical leadership EL was positively interrelated with employees' affective and normative commitment and was not correlated with employees' continuance commitment. Although the results of current study contradicted the findings of Eslamieh & Davoudi (2016), they did verify that a positive bond of Ethical leadership EL has been formatted with organizational commitment COC.

When testing the impact of Ethical leadership EL on teachers' loyalty TL, the current study has shown this to be important, as there is a statistically significant correlation and impact between Ethical leadership EL

perception and teachers' loyalty. This means that teachers' loyalty TL was greatly affected by the type of leadership style they experienced in the international schools in Jeddah city. This result accords with Yang's (2014) findings, which concluded that leaders' behaviours have a strong influence on teachers' job satisfaction, which positively reflects the subordinates' well-being and life satisfaction. Therefore, when employees reach this stage of well-being and satisfaction, they tend to feel loyal to the organisation. Hence, organisational leaders should keep in mind the importance of creating a positive working environment that contributes to creating a positive state of well-being and high levels of satisfaction for their employees.

The actions of the current study in testing teachers' loyalty TL as a mediator variable has proved that loyalty has transmitted the effect between Ethical leadership EL style and continuance organisational commitment COC in the international schools in Jeddah. Ethical leadership EL has no direct effect on organisational commitment COC, but it turns out to be more effective when teachers' loyalty TL is tied to the organisation. Leaders who behave ethically tend to increase employee loyalty to their organisation, thus their commitment towards the organisation is reinforced. Although, there is a difference in mediating variables between the current study and Yang's (2014) study, the results of both show that leadership has a strong influence on job satisfaction and continuance organizational commitment. That reflects the employees' well-being and life satisfaction positively, where employees' well-being and life satisfaction are increased, because they transfer the positive emotions and feelings from their working life to their home life.

7. Conclusion:

It was necessary to enhance the practice of Ethical leadership EL in the international schools in Jeddah in order to elicit positive changes in employees' continued organisational commitment COC. This is because teachers' loyalty was found to be effective in mediating the role between Ethical leadership EL and organisational commitment COC, and it was useful for managers in the organisation to improve the work environment that contributes to make employees feel proud to participate in the teamwork of the organization. To increase ethical behaviors in the work environment, organisations need those managers, supervisors and leaders who act ethically and impose ethical work values among the employees.

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